

TWO-PHASE PORO-VASCULAR LAMINATES WITH STRUCTURE-PLUS-SURFACE ROUGHNESS CONTROL

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1 Introduction

There is growing interest in novel multifunctional composite materials comprised of both solid and liquid components. NRL has been developing a new class of two-phase composites called poro-vascular composites (PVCs) with both structure and surface morphology (roughness) control functionality [1]. These are polymer laminates with an internal vascular network for the liquid phase that connects to sub-millimeter scale pore arrays on the surface. Active control of the liquid-phase height and meniscus shape within the pores (Figure 1) is expected to provide the capability for tailoring the surface morphology from dimpled to flat to domed. Liquid height control is being developed using volume-displacement pumping in the vascular channels, and liquid shape control at the pore exit is being developed using voltage induced changes in contact angle via electrode-wetting-on-dielectric (EWOD) phenomenon. Research has been focused on modeling and characterizing structural and fluidic behaviors, multifunctional design and optimization, and integration on low-Re airfoils for active control of boundary-layer flow.

PVC technology will enable system-level improvements in small UAV applications like drag reduction through aerodynamic boundary-layer flow control (e.g., switchable turbulence tripping on airfoils), controlled vascular heat flow transport, and/or switchable thermal dissipation at surfaces with minimal aerodynamic drag penalty. Novel air vehicle flight steering via profile drag and lift control may also be possible, which will allow for the replacement of standard flaps-servo hardware with PVC skin for critical weight reductions in nano-UAV systems (Figure 2).

This paper will report on recent progress in several areas including: mechanical properties of the polyimide films being used to make PVC prototypes; material-electrode effects on EWOD

control of liquid contact angles (meniscus shape) on flat substrates and within capillary geometries (pore-analog); and numerical modeling and wind tunnel testing of mm-scale surface roughness effects on boundary-layer flow over small UAV-scale airfoils. The paper begins by providing some background on: PVC solid-phase materials, design, and fabrication; liquid-phase materials and control; and roughness effects on boundary-layer flow over airfoils. The methods used are described next followed by results and discussion. The paper ends with a summary and conclusions for further work.

1.1 Solid-Phase Design and Prototyping

PVC prototypes are being designed and fabricated from micro-machined laminates of the following three polyimide films: Kapton RS (a bi-layered polyimide with one conductive layer; 2 mil thick total), Cirlex (10 mil thick), and Kapton HN (5 mil thick). Layer-to-layer bonding is done using an acrylic adhesive film, Pylux, in a hot-roll lamination process (Figure 3). Fabrication begins with bonding the Kapton RS and Cirlex layers together. Vascular channels are then laser micro-machined into the Cirlex layer followed by laser drilling through the channel bottoms to create pores in the top RS layer (Figure 4). Details of the laser micromachining setup and conditions have been reported previously [1]. Parylene C dielectric (~5 μm thick) is then vapor deposited on the machined sub-laminates as an electrical dielectric (isolation) layer for EWOD control. A thin layer of Teflon AF 1600 (~200 nm thick) hydrophobic coating is spin-coated on the top of the Parylene C to create non-wetting conditions at the pore exit/surface (Figure 5-left). The final step involves “capping” the channel side with the Kapton HN layer, to serve as the base of the composite. Vascular pumping for liquid height control is currently done using an external (syringe) pump connected with a flexible glass

capillary. Integration of the pumping directly within the vascular network is a longer-term goal.

In addition to providing structure function, the solid PVC phase must: contain the liquid-phase with minimal adverse coupling between mechanical deformations and liquid shape control functionality; scale in size ($> 10 \text{ cm}^2$) at reasonable costs; integrate with system structure in a “modular” fashion for easy removal and replacement with damage or loss of functionality; and allow for full integration of the fluidics sub-system and electrical connections.

1.2 Liquid Phase Control

Control of liquid phase in the pore and at the exit surface will be achieved by combining volumetric displacement pumping, for height control within the pore, with EWOD for meniscus shape control at the pore exit. A model has been developed to predict the effects of channel pumping and applied potential on liquid height and meniscus shape in a circular pore [1]. As liquid begins to “bulge” out of a pore, the curvature (and therefore pressure) increases until it reaches a maximum; beyond this, it decreases as the liquid spreads across the surface. If pressure-pumping is used, the liquid will spill uncontrollably from the pore after reaching the pressure inflection point. With volume-displacement pumping, this is avoided. However, an array of pores connected to a channel with volume-pumping can still exhibit siphon-spillage if there are any “significant” differences in individual pore diameters (different curvatures \rightarrow pressures).

Surface tension forces dominate at the PVC device scale leading to the following primary fluidic design parameters: geometry and dimensions of the pores and channels, and the pore and channel wall characteristics (e.g., material/coatings, roughness, etc.) that affect contact angle. For ideal conditions, the equilibrium contact angle, θ_0 , is governed by Young’s equation [2]:

$$\cos \theta_0 = \frac{\gamma_{SV} - \gamma_{SL}}{\gamma_{LV}} = \frac{\gamma_{SV} - \gamma_{SL}}{\gamma} \quad (1)$$

where γ_{SV} is the surface tension of the solid in contact with a vapor phase, γ_{SL} is the surface tension of the liquid in contact with the solid phase, and $\gamma_{LV} \equiv \gamma$ is the surface (interfacial) tension of the liquid in contact with the vapor phase. In Eq. (1), γ_{SV} and γ are intrinsic properties of the solid and liquid phases and can be quantified independently by

experiment. γ_{SL} is controlled by material factors and field conditions at the solid-liquid interface.

Preliminary NRL work showed large variability in channel-pore filling behavior. Certain channel branches and pores do not fill while others allow liquid to flow and spill out of them. Adding a flow constriction between the channel and the pores (see Figure 4) improved pore-filling uniformity, but it did not work reliably. Fluidics analysis and design is needed to achieve more robust control of liquid flow-displacement within the channel-pore networks and uniform filling of connected pores within an array. Surface Evolver software [3] is being explored for this purpose to model the effects of pore and channel dimensions and wetting conditions in simple configurations. More complex geometries will likely require the use of finite element methods, which have better automated meshing capabilities.

The liquid-phase meniscus shape in PVCs will be controlled using EWOD-based control of the contact angle at the pore walls. An applied potential between a conductive liquid and insulated electrode causes a reduction in contact angle by electrostatic forces [4] (Figure 5-right). The relationship between contact angle, θ , and applied potential is given by the Lippmann-Young equation:

$$\cos \theta = \cos \theta_0 + \frac{\epsilon_0 \epsilon}{2\gamma t} V^2 \quad (2)$$

where θ_0 is the contact angle (equilibrium) at zero applied voltage (given by Eq. (1)), ϵ_0 the permittivity of free space, ϵ the dielectric constant of the dielectric, γ the liquid phase interfacial tension, t the dielectric-hydrophobic layer thickness, and V the applied voltage. Contact angle decreases with applied voltage (positive or negative) until saturation occurs, which has been observed from 15 to 95 degrees [5, 6]. Saturation is not fully understood at present. Several mechanisms have been proposed, including: voltage breakdown and charge trapping in the dielectric layer [7, 8]; voltage breakdown in the vapor phase at the droplet-solid contact line [9]; and finite electrical conductivity of the liquid phase [10].

EWOD experiments characterizing changes in contact angle with applied potential are typically conducted with aqueous solutions on flat, electroded substrates (e.g., silicon wafers, ITO glass, etc.). Several more recent investigations have utilized ionic liquids (IL’s) [6, 11-15], which are room temperature “molten salts” with positive and negative charged species only (i.e., no solvent). IL’s

have very low vapor pressures, which makes them ideal for PVC applications where little or no liquid phase evaporation is desired. Mixed results have been reported relative to Lippmann-Young behavior with IL's [6, 11]. Some report smaller than expected contact angle changes with voltage [12, 13] or large hysteresis effects [15].

Adapting EWOD for meniscus shape control in PVCs requires extension to new geometries (capillaries), non-uniform electroding that extends only a short distance from the surface into the capillary, and non-ideal substrates (rougher and more flexible). Early work with EWOD in a capillary was performed by Prins et al. [16]; they demonstrated EWOD-based height control of a liquid in an array of hexagonal capillaries ($\sim 350 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter) in a honeycomb made with metalized-polymer walls electrically insulated by a hydrophobic-dielectric coating. They used an immiscible two-layer liquid system consisting of an aqueous salt solution and non-polar oil to create larger changes in capillary pressure with changes in contact angle to achieve larger rises of salt solution within the capillaries with applied voltage. However, these fully electroded capillary walls are more similar to flat electrode configurations than to the electroding configuration used in PVCs.

1.3 Roughness Effects on Boundary-Layer Flow

The effect of surface roughness on boundary layer flow over airfoils is not completely understood, particularly in the transitional Reynolds (Re) number regime where a substantial portion of the flow is laminar. These cases are susceptible to boundary layer "bubble" separation, which leads to significant increases in drag and decreases in lift that may lead to "stall" (see Figure 4.43 in [17]).

Unmanned air vehicles (UAVs) operating in the low Reynold's number flight regime often utilize "trip strips" (e.g., strip of tape across the span) at a fixed chord location on the airfoil to induce transition to attached turbulent boundary-layer flow. A trip strip may increase the skin-friction drag, but this is compensated for by avoidance of a laminar separation bubble. Attached laminar flow is optimal (minimal drag), but maintaining laminar conditions for all flight conditions may not be possible, particularly with increasing angles of attack.

Simulating surface roughness effects on boundary-layer flow can be accomplished by explicitly resolving the roughness features in the boundary-layer and solving the Navier-Stokes

equations over a very fine, isotropic grid. However, this approach is computationally expensive. A less costly approach is to solve Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations, which model the statistically-steady effects of the turbulence on the mean flow field. For large Reynolds number flows, these turbulence models give satisfactory results. However, they have not been designed for analysis in the transitional-Re regime. Rumsey and Spalart, for example, found large discrepancies in predicted transition locations on a smooth NACA 0012 airfoil using these types of turbulence models [18]. Other attempts have been made to specifically model the laminar-to-turbulence transition with varying degrees of success [19-21].

In this work, the Leibeck LA 2573A airfoil has been used for both numerical modeling and wind tunnel experiments. This is a low pitching moment airfoil with a thickness of 13.7% of the chord, c , and it has been extensively characterized in wind tunnel tests. It employs a upper surface trip-strip at the 24% chord point ($x/c = 0.24$) to avoid separation bubbles at the low Reynolds numbers for which it is typically used: 100,000 to 500,000.

Table 1 shows the effect of trip strip height on the drag coefficient, c_D , for the LA 2573A airfoil at $\text{Re} = 250,000$ (fixed lift coefficient typical of cruise) determined in wind tunnel experiments [22]. The effect of a trip-strip on c_D for this airfoil has been analyzed using XFOIL, an airfoil design software that uses a high-order (2-D flow) panel method with strongly coupled viscid-inviscid interactions. Computed drag for a smooth LA 2573A at $\text{Re} = 200,000$ gave: $c_D = 0.0194$, and with a trip-strip at $x/c = 0.24$: $c_D = 0.0135$. This is a 30% reduction in drag between the turbulent and laminar flows! Table 2 lists the calculated maximum trip-strip heights for the LA 2573A at $x/c = 0.24$ for Mach number 0 to 5 that avoid any penalties in skin-friction drag [23]. Table 1 and Table 2 provide lower and upper bounds on trip strip height for the LA 2573A airfoil.

The trips-strips are chord-wise located on the airfoil to achieve "optimal" performance during the primary flight regime (e.g., steady-cruise). However, this chord-wise location may not be optimal for other flight regimes. For example, drag can be greatly reduced during level flight at sub-cruise velocities by not having any trip-strip. In other flight regimes, it can be reduced by altering its chord-wise location. Multifunctional PVCs may

enable new opportunities for tailoring trip-strip characteristics like: on-off, shape and height, and chord-wise location. This can be used to achieve significant gains in UAV aerodynamic performance and efficiency over all flight regimes.

2 Methods

2.1 Mechanical characterization

Tensile testing was performed on several component materials and PVC prototypes to determine their stress-strain behavior and their elastic modulus and ultimate strength properties. Four or five rectangular test specimens were cut from Cirlex, Kapton RS, and Kapton HN sheets in longitudinal and transverse orientations (Table 3). Test specimens were also extracted from several PVC prototypes in the pore-channel regions.

Testing was performed on an MTS Insight 100 test system with a 1 kN load cell and pneumatic grips (Instron 2712-003; 1 kN capacity) with flat-smooth steel inserts (1 x 1.5 inch face) and 90 psi actuation pressure. Specimen extension in the gage section was measured using a large displacement extensometer (MTS XLT; 970 mm) with optical encoded sensing. Thin strips of two-sided adhesive film were placed across the width of the specimen on both sides under the extensometer knife-edge attachments to prevent slipping. The crosshead displacement rate was set at 2.0 mm/min for all tests resulting in an effective strain rate of 0.03 to 0.06 s⁻¹ on the specimens during testing. Load, crosshead, and extensometer displacement data were collected every 0.1 sec during testing. Young's modulus, E , values were calculated from the load-crosshead displacement data and specimen geometry using:

$$E = \frac{dP}{d\delta} \times \frac{l}{A} \quad (3)$$

where P is the applied load, δ is the crosshead displacement, l is the specimen length between the grip-edges, and A is the cross-section area ignoring the existence of pores and channels. The load-displacement slope, $dP/d\delta$, was calculated from a least-squares line fit in the low-load region. The data for fitting were selected to maximize the slope value. The starting point was taken at or near the initial (zero) load-displacement value. The endpoint was manually selected so as to maximize the slope value and generally corresponded with a load ~5-15% of peak during testing. Reported ultimate strength values correspond to the peak load divided by original cross-section area.

2.2 EWOD materials and characterization

Flat substrate EWOD experiments were performed on conductive polyimide films: Kapton 200RS100 (roughness $R_a = 80$ nm) and Kapton 275XC (roughness $R_a = 250$ nm) and compared with EWOD results from a gold-coated silicon wafer. The conductive substrates were coated with 5 μm of Parylene C via vapor deposition performed by Specialty Coating Systems. They were then spin-coated with a 2% solution (by weight) of Teflon 1600 AF dissolved in Fluorinert FC-40 (BP ~ 165 deg C) followed by baking at 170 deg C for 5-7 minutes. This created a ~200 nm thick coating of Teflon for surface hydrophobicity. Three liquids were tested in EWOD: 0.1 M NaCl (Aq), 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium acetate (IL2), and 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium methyl sulfate (IL4).

An FTA1000 system was used for the EWOD measurements with a 30 gage needle for providing fluidic and electric control of the droplet. Current between the fluid and electrode was monitored to ensure that dielectric breakdown did not occur, and the test was stopped if current exceeded 1 μA . The test procedure consisted of depositing a small (<1 μL) droplet on the substrate surface and applying a fixed potential. Liquid was then pumped into the droplet at a rate of 2 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ while holding the potential constant and measuring the droplet's advancing contact angle. Upon reaching a diameter of 2-3 mm (~4-6 μL), the pump was reversed, extracting liquid at a rate of 2 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ while holding the potential constant and measuring the droplet's receding contact angle. The average of the advancing and receding angle values is reported in this work. This procedure of measuring both advancing and receding angles as a function of voltage gives more accurate and repeatable results than the typical EWOD procedure, which holds droplet volume constant while varying the potential.

Glass capillary samples (1.5 mm OD, 1.1 mm ID) were electroded for EWOD at one end. First, the EWOD end was mechanically polished to achieve a flat and smooth surface perpendicular to the axis. It was then "stamped" onto a thin liquid film of Cabot CCI-300 silver nanoink that coated the end and wicked < 0.2 mm up the inside and outside walls of the capillary. A fine line of the silver nanoink was painted on the outside as a connecting lead. The nanoink was then cured at 175 deg C for 45 min. After drying, they were sent for coating with ~5 μm of Parylene C (vapor deposition; Specialty

Coating Systems). They were then dipped in a 1% solution (by weight) of Teflon 1600 AF in Fluorinert FC-72 (BP ~56 deg C). Excess liquid was blown-off the capillary using compressed air. They were baked in a vacuum oven at 70 deg C for up to 3 days.

EWOD testing with the capillaries was challenging due to the difficulty in observing the contact angle on the ID walls when backlit. Fluorescein disodium salt (D&C Yellow #8) was dissolved into 0.1 M NaCl solution at a concentration of 0.001 mg/mL. A 405 nm blue laser was used to illuminate the capillary liquid, and it was video imaged through a 550 ± 50 nm optical bandpass filter for better contrast. Higher concentrations of the Fluorescein produced brighter images, but also increased the contact angle hysteresis. Contact angles of 120 deg (advancing) and 104 (receding) were measured while pumping the fluorescent solution into the capillary at 0.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, which is similar to that expected for pure 0.1 M NaCl solutions. Capillary EWOD testing was performed by manipulating the voltage on the silver nanoink electrode while keeping the liquid connected to ground.

2.3 Wind tunnel characterization

The wind tunnel used was a low-speed (13-100 m/s), closed-throat, single-return, atmospheric facility with a square 1.2 m x 1.2 m test section with filleted corners, and the sting-balance specifications:

- Normal force: 333 N max; accuracy = 0.09 N
- Axial force: 67 N max; accuracy = 0.04 N
- Yaw moment: 2.8 N-m max; accuracy = 0.002 N-m

The LA 2573A airfoil had a 0.61 m span, 0.2 m chord, c , and $0.137c$ thickness. Attachment to the sting-balance was made at the trailing edge of the airfoil at the centerline. The airfoil was constructed with a fiber-glass skin and a foam core. A shallow slot (35 mm wide x 1 mm deep) was milled into the upper surface across the span centered about the $x/c = 0.24$ chord location. This is so that PVC test patches could be integrated into the airfoil without creating vertical seams that would disrupt or alter the boundary-layer flows.

A series of tests were planned to characterize the effects of various airfoil surface conditions; they are listed in Table 4 and shown schematically in Figure 6. A smooth LA 2573A airfoil was tested for baseline performance purposes. Silicone-rubber “static PVC analog” patches 1.0 mm thick with 1.0 mm diameter semi-spheres (0.5 mm

protrusion height) in linear and staggered arrays were molded for use in the wind tunnel tests (Figure 7). The effect of (classical) trip-strip height on lift and drag was assessed to verify the minimum height required to avoid bubble separation. Testing of an alternative PVC patch trip-strip was also planned to assess its ability for tripping the boundary layer flow. Several other PVC patch configurations were tested to assess their affects on lift and drag and their ability to provide steering forces depending on their configuration and location on the airfoil.

2.4 Computational modeling

Two-dimensional air flow over the LA 2573A airfoil with chord-length, $c = 0.202$ m, was analyzed. An O-grid was generated to surround the airfoil out to a radial distance of $450c$ with a minimum wall-normal grid spacing in the boundary layer of 0.0002 m. Grid points were clustered in the streamwise (“ x ”) direction near the leading and trailing edges of the airfoil, and near the center, thin anisotropic quadrilateral cells conform to the surface. Inflow conditions were $Re = 200,000$ based on c , giving a Mach number of 0.2. Compressibility effects were expected to be negligible under these conditions, and time step restrictions associated with low Mach number flows should be comparable to those required for the viscous effects. Riemann far-field conditions were used with the specified inflow conditions necessary to achieve the desired Re and Mach number values. No-slip conditions were imposed on the airfoil surface.

Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations were solved using a realizable $k-\epsilon$ model for the turbulence closure, where k is the turbulence kinetic energy parameter and ϵ is the turbulence dissipation rate. The RANS equations were solved up to the wall without the use of empirical wall functions, which amounts to setting $k = 0$ and $d\epsilon/dn = 0$ where n is the direction normal to the surface.

Two airfoil surface conditions were considered. The first surface was perfectly smooth, and the second incorporates a patch of 2 mm diameter semi-cylinders (PVC analog; axis along wing span) separated 1 mm edge-to-edge on the top of the airfoil over $0.12 \leq x/c \leq 0.30$.

Two different strategies for dealing with the laminar-to-turbulent transition were employed. The first explicitly modeled the PVC roughness features that block the boundary layer cells and act as source terms for production of k . In the second, turbulence production levels were increased in regions of strong

laminar flow curvature, which indicates separation. The equations were solved using a pre-conditioned, compressible Navier-Stokes, finite-volume solver in the CFD++ software, which uses a Riemann solver to compute the convective fluxes. Implicit time integration and dual time-stepping were used to rapidly converge to the steady state solution.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Mechanical properties

Figure 8 shows typical stress-strain curves for the PVC material components in both the longitudinal and transverse directions. Curves for two prototype PVC's are also shown. Figure 9 shows tensile modulus and ultimate strength values for the material components in both the longitudinal and transverse directions.

The results show that the mechanical performance in the transverse direction is slightly better (stiffer and stronger) than in the longitudinal direction for all materials. The differences are probably not significant, and selection of the layer orientations during lamination can be used to minimize or maximize anisotropy. The Cirlex-T exhibited the largest modulus, and the Kapton-HN-T exhibited the highest strength. Kapton RS exhibited lower modulus and strength than either of the other two materials. HN showed the highest elongation followed by the RS and then the Cirlex.

The stress-strain behavior of the PVC prototype falls significantly below that of the component materials (Figure 8) due to the pore and channel cut-outs in the gage section. These prototypes (#5/6) consisted of one layer of Cirlex, with pores and channels machined, bonded to Kapton HN on the channel side. The pores were 1 mm in diameter with 1 mm edge-to-edge spacing in both directions for a 20% pore areal density. The entire gage section of the test specimens was covered with pores and channels, and the channels were aligned with the loading axis. The average measured modulus was 1460 MPa, and the average measured ultimate strength was 71.5 MPa.

Theoretical predictions of the average tensile modulus for two laminate configurations, without pores or channels, were: RS-Cirlex-HN = 3085 MPa, and Cirlex-HN = 3145 MPa (PVC prototype configuration). Strength predictions were governed by failure of the weakest component material, the Kapton RS, and gave: RS-Cirlex-HN = 114 MPa, and Cirlex-HN = 160 MPa. The averages found in testing (Figure 8): $E = 1460$ MPa, and $S =$

71.5 MPa represent a ~55% decline in property values, apparently due to the pore and channel material cut-outs.

3.2 EWOD behavior

Figure 10 shows contact angle change with applied voltage on the Kapton RS substrate for the three tested liquids with the accompanying Lippmann-Young fit. The primary observed effect of liquid composition is a change in the zero voltage contact angle (θ_0): Aq (111 deg), IL4 (98 deg), and IL2 (92 deg). This correlates with their decreasing interfacial tension, γ , (0.072 N/m, 0.053 N/m, and 0.043 N/m, respectively) and is consistent with contact angle physics models. The semi-empirical model proposed by Good & Girifalco [24]:

$$\gamma_{SL} = \gamma_{S0} + \gamma - 2\Phi\sqrt{\gamma_{S0} \times \gamma} \quad (4)$$

accounts for the effect of the liquid's interfacial tension on the surface energy of the solid-liquid interface, γ_{SL} . In Eq. (4), γ_{S0} is the solid-vapor surface tension in vacuum (which is assumed to be approximately equal to γ_{SV}), and Φ is a function of molecular properties of the solid and liquid materials and has been shown to be between 0.5 and 1.3 [2]. Inserting Eq. (4) into Eq. (1) and simplifying gives:

$$\cos \theta_0 = \text{constant} \times \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_{SV}}{\gamma}} - 1, \quad (5)$$

which predicts a decreasing θ_0 with decreasing γ . In contrast, there was little or no difference in EWOD data from the same liquid on different substrates, which also is in agreement with Lippmann-Young Eq. (2), where the only effect of the solid is the dielectric thickness and properties, which were identical for all three tested substrates.

Figure 11 summarizes the EWOD data for the three liquids averaged across all substrates. The key finding here is that all three liquids saturate at a common contact angle value (~80 deg), regardless of liquid or substrate. Minimizing the angle of saturation is desirable for applications because it increases the total change in contact angle with applied potential. Methods to reduce the saturation contact angle have been proposed, like different dielectric coating materials and thicknesses, and AC rather than DC applied potential. An investigation to better understand the independence of saturation angle with liquid-type is ongoing.

A series of video still photographs showing liquid height and meniscus control in a capillary is

shown in Figure 12. The meniscus is difficult to see in some of these photographs, and the red curves have been added to indicate the meniscus locations. The video permits better discernment of the meniscus than is possible with the individual still photographs. Analysis of the video shows that a ~ 70 degree change in contact angle occurred with a change in applied potential: 110 deg at 0 V versus 40 deg at 200 V (angles relative to the pore wall). These contact angle changes were repeatable with changes in applied potential.

These initial capillary experiments show a much greater range in contact angle change with potential (70 degrees) compared to the flat-substrate results (~ 30 degrees or less). This is thought to be due to the different electrode-liquid geometries of the two EWOD systems. The reduction of contact angle with applied potential for a flat substrate is governed by a balance between the liquid's surface tension and the (ionic) charge repulsion forces at the solid-liquid interface. Surface tension acts to minimize the liquid-air and liquid-solid surface areas while charge repulsion at the solid-liquid interface acts to spread the drop [4].

In contrast, the extent of electroding within the capillary ID is limited to a small band at the exit (Figure 5-left). EWOD within the capillary still involves a balance between surface tension and charge repulsion, but the equilibrium configuration is constrained by the limited electroded area. As the meniscus advances closer to the electrode, the contact angle remains unchanged (nonwetting) up to some point where a transition occurs with the circumferential contact line "jumping" up to the electrode region and changing from nonwetting to wetting contact angle. The contact line remains confined within this electrode zone while liquid is pumped-in resulting in a gradual increase in curvature to flat meniscus and then bulging from the capillary exit (dimpled to flat to domed per Figure 1). Conversely, as liquid is extracted, the contact line remains pinned to the electrode region until some minimum contact angle is reached that is much smaller (~ 35 deg) than that observed for flat-plate EWOD. The contact line eventually "de-pins" as the meniscus recedes from the electrode, and the contact angle re-establishes its nonwetting value.

3.3 Wind tunnel measurements

Figure 13 shows lift and drag data for the LA 2573A airfoil with a smooth surface and with the 0.457 mm high trip-strip at $x/c = 0.24$. The 0.457

mm high trip-strip provided the greatest reduction in drag. In typical applications, this airfoil is operated in steady-cruise at $Re \sim 200,000$ to $400,000$ with an angle of attack of 6 degrees, which corresponds to a lift coefficient value of 0.55. Under these conditions, the drag coefficient in the untripped configuration is: $c_D = 0.16$, and with the trip-strip: $c_D = 0.12$. This is a 25% reduction, which is close to the 30% difference predicted by the XFOIL 2-D Airfoil code described in the introduction.

The wind tunnel experiment to assess the tripping capability of a span-wise 38 mm wide PVC patch is ongoing due to delays caused by wind tunnel equipment problems. However, given that the standard 3.175 mm W x 0.475 mm H rectangular trip-strip functions well at tripping the flow, it seems likely that the 38 mm wide PVC patch with 0.5 mm high semi-spherical dome roughness elements should also trip the flow.

The next series of experiments looked at the effect of PVC roughness patches placed on the airfoil topside at the outboard tip regions, extending from the back edge of the 3.175 mm x 0.475 mm trip-strip to the trailing edge within the adverse pressure gradient portion of the turbulent boundary layer. In other words, these tests assessed whether the 0.5 mm high roughness features were large enough to induce an increase in skin friction drag for potential aircraft steering applications. No measurable effect was observed for the symmetric blank (smooth) patches. A slight increase in drag was observed for symmetric placement of PVC domed patches on the airfoil (bottom left of Figure 6). For the non-symmetric bump-smooth patch configuration (bottom right of Figure 6), an increasing yaw moment occurs with increasing angle of attack (AoA) (Figure 14). The magnitude is relatively small (0.005 at 7 degrees AoA), but it should be sufficient to steer the vehicle under typical mission flight conditions.

3.4 Numerical predictions

The predicted turbulence kinetic energy fields generated in the boundary layer flows over the LA 2573A model airfoil pitched at 0 degrees to the incoming flow are shown in Figure 15. The solid red line shows the transition behavior predicted by the $k-\epsilon$ model for an airfoil with a smooth surface. Transition is indicated by the sudden increase of k values in going from the leading-edge (LE) to trailing-edge (TE). The black dashed line shows the transition behavior for the same airfoil with a 2-D

PVC analog consisting of a span-wise patch of semi-cylindrical roughness elements, 2 mm in diameter, positioned between $0.12 \leq x/c \leq 0.30$ on the chord. The turbulence-energy k values indicate that the transition point is moved upstream from $x/c \approx 0.35$ for the smooth condition to the front-edge of the PVC patch ($x/c = 0.12$). While not shown in this paper, this effect was found to be less pronounced at higher angles of attack (e.g., 10 degrees) where the transition point for the smooth airfoil also moves forward towards the LE and roughly coincides with the front-edge of the PVC patch. These findings support the notion that the PVC surface morphology (1 mm high semi-spherical domes) can initiate boundary-layer tripping.

Figure 16 shows lift and drag coefficient plots computed for the LA2573A airfoil with either smooth or PVC roughness conditions on the skin at various angles of attack. The boundary layer is called “untripped” for natural transition on the smooth airfoil and “tripped” for roughness-induced transition with the PVC patch.

The lift data in Figure 16 shows essentially no difference between the smooth and PVC airfoils. However, conclusions are somewhat complicated by the fact that the numerical simulation cannot capture laminar bubble separation (stall) on the smooth airfoil at the higher angles of attack. This is expected to increase the drag experienced by the smooth airfoil significantly beyond that which would be experienced by the PVC airfoil, and is indicated notionally by the red-dashed line.

There is a notable difference in predicted drag between the two airfoil roughness conditions. The current simulation captures the effects of skin-friction drag and indicates that roughness via PVC or otherwise creates drag forces, such as the yaw forces observed experimentally in the wind tunnel.

4 Summary and Future Work:

The work and findings reported in this paper have provided a better understanding of the technical challenges associated with designing and fabricating multifunctional PVCs. Fluidic control, structure-fluidic coupling, and roughness affects on the boundary-layer flow over low-Reynolds airfoils are key areas requiring further research.

Modeling and experiments showed that mm-scale surface roughness features influence transition, drag, and lift behavior on a small UAV airfoil (LA 2573A) in an operational flight regime. Modeling showed that tripping (laminar to turbulent transition)

occurred with a patch of 1 mm semi-spherical protrusions towards the leading edge, with further support by wind-tunnel results that demonstrated transition with an even smaller 0.5 mm high span-wise surface ledge (trip-strip). Non-symmetric placement of surface roughness (PVC patches) on the topside of the airfoil (0.5 mm bumps on one side, smooth on the other) demonstrated the development of a yaw moment that could be used for aircraft steering, and modeling showed increases in skin-friction drag with PVC patching. While these results are preliminary, they support the notion of using PVCs for active control of surface roughness for improved aerodynamic performance and efficiency.

The novel demonstration of EWOD in a capillary showed significant amplification of contact angle change with applied potential that raises new questions. The 70 degree change with applied potential, from an average non-wetting angle of 110 degrees at 0 V to an average wetting angle of 40 degrees at 200 V, was more than double the angle change observed in the flat plate EWOD tests with identical electrode-coating parameters. Another key result was the demonstration of Lippmann-Young EWOD behavior with ILs in the flat substrate experiments, contrary to two prior studies [12, 13]. The ILs, however, showed significantly less change in angle with potential than the aqueous solution. This potential limitation, which is due to saturation at the relatively large ~ 80 degree angle for all tested liquids, points to the need for further understanding of EWOD saturation.

Mechanical testing demonstrated a range of useful stiffness and strength values from the candidate polyimide component materials. The addition of machined channels and pores in laminate prototypes resulted in a $\sim 55\%$ decrease in modulus and strength. Improvements are expected with future design refinements and investigation to better understand how the pores and channels and their configuration influence mechanical properties, their anisotropy, and the coupling between mechanical deformation on liquid phase behavior and control.

Planned future work on fluidic control includes: refinements of the capillary experiment to advance scientific understanding of EWOD in these new geometries; the development and characterization of PVC laminate prototypes in single- and multi-pore configurations (e.g., 2x2 and 4x4 arrays); and external and internal vascular liquid-displacement pumping. These prototypes will also provide useful test-beds for characterizing

coupling between liquid height and meniscus shape control and the mechanical deformations of the laminate and boundary-layer flows over the surface.

Much better understanding of the effects of mm-scale roughness on boundary-layer flow with low-Reynolds airfoils is needed to help guide the design of PVCs for performance enhancement in specific UAV applications. For example, how does the scale and configuration of the surface roughness and its location on the airfoil effect the boundary-layer flow? What are the best airfoil configurations and flight regimes for performance enhancement by PVC technology? Large-eddy simulations will be explored to better capture the inherently unsteady, three-dimensional phenomena occurring in the boundary layer of PVC skin airfoils. Advancements in methods for integrating PVC prototypes with the wind tunnel airfoil models are also needed to eliminate or mitigate surface discontinuities at the PVC-airfoil interfaces. These can overwhelm the PVC roughness effects on the boundary-layer flow. Success will enable more accurate measurements of transition and drag/lift and guide the integration of PVC skin in future UAV applications.

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6 Tables

Trip Strip Height [mm]	Drag Coefficient, c_D	Lift Coefficient, c_L
0.000, free transition	0.020	0.55
0.152	0.015	0.55
0.305	0.010	0.55

Table 1: Trip-strip height effects on drag and lift coefficients for the LA 2573A airfoil at $Re = 250,000$ when placed at $x/c = 0.24$ [22].

Reynold's number, Re	Maximum trip-strip height, h [mm]
200,000	0.483
250,000	0.406

Table 2: Calculated maximum trip-strip height at $x/c = 0.24$ for the LA 2573A airfoil at $Re = 250,000$ that results in no skin friction drag penalty [23].

Material	Avg. Thickness [mm]	Avg. Width [mm]	Avg. Length [mm]	Number Tested
Kapton 200RS100, L	0.065	25.46	115.2	5
Kapton 200RS100, T	0.064	25.38	126.3	4
Cirlex 1000CL, L	0.258	12.81	125.7	4
Cirlex 1000CL, T	0.254	12.86	126.0	4
Kapton HN, L	0.127	25.48	113.1	5
Kapton HN, T	0.128	25.57	127.3	4
Prototypes 5/6: Cirlex-Pyralux-Kapton HN	0.401	14.98	76.0	2

Table 3: Mechanical test sample materials and dimensions.

Airfoil Configuration	Test Purpose
Smooth	Baseline
Standard rectangular trip-strips: 3.175 mm W x 0.305, 0.457, or 0.711 mm H on smooth airfoil centered at $x/c = 0.24$	Comparison of drag and lift coefficients with baseline
PVC trip-strips: staggered array 38 mm W x 1.0 mm semi-sphere in slot centered at $x/c = 0.24$	Demonstration of PVC tripping capability
Rectangular trip-strip: 3.175 mm W x 0.457 mm H at $x/c = 0.24$ plus PVC patches on airfoil top, symmetric at outboard edges	Assessment of PVC effects on skin friction drag
Rectangular trip-strip: 3.175 mm W x 0.457 mm H at $x/c = 0.24$ plus PVC and blank patches on airfoil top, anti-symmetric at outboard edges	Assessment of PVC skin friction drag for yaw moment steering potential

Table 4: Wind tunnel test configurations.

7 Figures

Figure 1. Liquid configurations for a circular pore. Liquid height is controlled by pumping in the vascular channels, and meniscus shape is controlled changes in contact angle via electrode-wetting-on-dielectric.

Figure 2. Notional unmanned air vehicle with PVC skin covering the airfoil for control of boundary-layer (BL) tripping and surface friction drag steering.

Figure 3. PVC laminates and flat-substrate EWOD cross-sections. (Top) functional PVC prototype configuration; (bottom) mechanical test configurations (PVC #5 & #6).

Figure 4. PVC prototype laminate. (Left) channel-side view showing a filling-channel on the left for connection to a flexible glass-capillary and external pump. (Right) channel and pore machining details.

Figure 5. (L) Cross-section view of a PVC pore showing the configuration for EWOD at the pore surface exit; (R) Flat EWOD setup and notional change in contact angle versus applied potential.

Figure 6. Airfoil patching configurations used in wind tunnel testing.

Figure 7. Silicone rubber molded PVC skin patch with 1.0 mm diameter semi-spherical protruding domes that are staggered row-to-row.

Figure 8. Typical stress-strain behavior for the PVC components and a prototype with 1 mm dia. pores (~20% areal coverage) and channels in the gage section.

Figure 9. Modulus/strength values for PVC components in longitudinal (L) and transverse (T) orientations.

Figure 10. Flat-plate EWOD results showing effect of different liquids. The points are experimental data, and the curves are Lippmann-Young equation fits to the "bold" data points.

Figure 11. Flat-plate EWOD results averaged over all substrates. The band shows the common saturation angle, and the error bars represent \pm standard deviation of all data at a given liquid/voltage combination.

Figure 12. EWOD in a glass capillary showing behavior under non-wetting (top; $V = 0$) and wetting (bottom; $V \neq 0$) conditions for different liquid heights.

Figure 13. Lift versus drag measurements for the LA 2573A airfoil with and without a trip-strip. The trip-strip significantly reduces drag under higher lift conditions corresponding to larger angles of attack.

Figure 14. Development of yaw moment with non-symmetric PVC patching on the airfoil topside.

Figure 15. Turbulence energy values for an LA 2573A airfoil with a smooth (red) and a PVC (black) surface.

The PVC patch shows the transition to a turbulent boundary-layer closer to the leading edge of the airfoil. Plots of the turbulence over the airfoils are shown in the insets with the PVC case on top and smooth on bottom.

Figure 16. Predicted lift and drag coefficients for the LA 2573A airfoil with smooth or PVC patched top surface. The dashed red line is the expected behavior for a smooth airfoil undergoing bubble-separation flow at higher AoA.

8 References

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